

THE SPECIFICITY OF THE FUNCTIONING OF THE ERGONYM IN ACTUAL ONOMASTICS

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Modern ergonomics is experiencing a state of “nominal explosion”: new complex objects (enterprises, organizations, travel agencies, shops, beauty salons, etc.) are constantly appearing, which receive individual names, and old names are replaced by new ones that correspond to the spirit of the time.

However, the question remains, what should be the ergonym in accordance with the social order? The occurrence of names is often random, and therefore functions chaotically. This is due to the fact that naming in the field of ergonomics is carried out without relying on a theoretical basis: at best, copywriters become nominees, but most often, this role is played by the direct owners of the urban service sector facility. Such chaotic naming gives rise to a lot of unmotivated names, most often having the character of borrowings from other languages. J. K. Werkman draws attention to this problem in his research: “A poorly chosen name will always be a hindrance, no matter how much money is invested in advertising. It is necessary to study the impact not only of the word itself, but also of its etymology and environment” .

In addition, under the conditions of the "onomastic explosion" it is difficult to explore the living world of constantly changing, appearing and dying names: each of the ergonyms performs a complex of different functions and contains a certain set of meanings. Thus, the same lexical unit acquires a special meaning, becoming the name of various objects. For example, the phrase "sunny house" in the name of a kindergarten becomes a symbol of a bright and carefree childhood; in the name of the repair and construction cooperative, it symbolizes the colorful palette of interior decoration; in the name of the store indicates television equipment, etc.

Note that ergonyms perform functions that are inherent in the onomastic system only to them: the advertising function and the function of motivation. On the other hand, onomatologists believe that the elements of the ergonymic system, due to the implementation of the connotative aspect of the semantics of ergonyms, are directed directly at the potential consumer in order to interest him, to become the object of his attention.

The connotative aspect of the ergonym has an extralinguistic nature and directly affects the competitiveness of the ergonym. When naming, the emotional and evaluative relations of the subject to the ergonym come to the fore: associations, motivation, expression, etc. Various factors can be involved in the formation of the connotative aspect of the semantics of ergonyms - from sound associations to associations that arise in the course of rethinking the meaning.

Associations arising from the perception of an ergonym can be divided into direct and indirect. The latter, in turn, are divided into the following associative series: national-cultural associative, regional, cultural-historical, socio-stratification, evaluative, aesthetic associative, emotionally expressive associative, artistic associative .

Socially conditioned N.V. Shimkevich names such ergonyms that use various philosophical, political, social and other ideas that are popular among the population and often have the character of mythologems. The linguist proposes to highlight the "pro-Western" peak of the early 90s of the XX century (beauty salons Julia, Chantal and many others) and the complex of "parochial" ideas of the late 90s. (cafe Marusya, hotel complex Boyarin). And culturally conditioned ergonyms are ergonyms, in which the nomination is based on concepts that, to one degree or another, belong to the category of eternal values and do not depend on the situation (works of literature and art, historical realities, etc.): Ruslan and Lyudmila, Veles, Prometheus , Cleopatra, Caesar, etc.

In actual ergonomics, there are many classifications of commercial nominations: M.G. Kurbanova distributes ergonyms in terms of motivational attitudes, T.A. Novozhilova proposes a classification according to the degree of accuracy in indicating ergonyms to the named object (that is, according to the degree of necessity in the naming of the nomenclature term), M.E. Novochikhina identifies three grounds for classifying a commercial nomination (according to the degree of motivation, according to the structure of the nomination - into single-word and compound ones, "according to the degree of transparency"). These and other classifications are united by the need to clarify the main functions of the ergonym.

Ergonyms can contain information of two types: advertising and rational. Advertising information is an excretory and evaluative characteristic of various kinds. Rational information most often informs (directly or indirectly) about the object of sale (Bread, Gardener, etc.), that is, it performs an informative function. Descriptive names are focused exclusively on the informative function (Shop of unique goods, Salon of knitwear, etc.). Information about the object of sale can

be expressed in different ways - proper names of direct, associative, figurative and symbolic nomination. It is also worth noting conditional-symbolic names, which should be divided into informative (Fish, Milk, Vegetables), advertising (Leader, Spartak, Rus) and advertising-informative. The last ergonyms are considered the most effective, since such names inform about the object and at the same time give the organization a high rating, for example, Comfort, Fashion House, Lux Furniture, etc.

But such ergonyms are not always successful, since there is a difficulty in isolating certain rational information about the object of sale. For example, today there are diversified organizations offering a variety of goods, and they cannot have informative names, since the only rational information that such ergonyms can contain is an indication of the diversity of the proposed range: Station wagon, For the future, 1000 trifles, etc. In most cases, diversified firms are forced to use only advertising names: Titan, Magnet, Auchan, etc. Advertising names are used in actual ergonomics very widely for objects of various profiles, including those who could use informative ergonyms, since the nominators consider advertising names more catchy and memorable.

As can be seen from this list, such a variety of names says of different denotative representation of the term - what type of associations can be indicated by him, about the possibility of various approaches to the study ergonymy. For example, A. A. Stambrovskaya narrows the scope of the concept of ergonym, excluding from it the names of societies, unions, circles, and A. M. Emelyanova and A. E. Yakovleva expand, including also the names of buildings various functional profiles (houses, enterprises, firms, shops, sports complexes, markets, cinemas, etc.). N.V. Podolskaya, on the other hand, specifically stipulates that the ergonym can turn into oikodomonym, if we are talking about a topographic object - the name of a building, structure. In turn, N.V. Shimkevich proposes to distinguish ergonyms - proper names of enterprises as business associations of people and temonyms - their names as subjects of law.

On the whole, it can be concluded that such a polynomial testifies to the terminological disorder of this area onomatology, including the lack of a common idea about the place of the ergonym in term hierarchies.

It should be noted that among ergonyms related to trade, names or names of bazaars (open markets) occupy the main place. Titles they were given mainly by the names of the main goods, which sold there, for example: «Балиқ бозор» («Fish market»), «Машина бозор» («Car market»), «Уй бозор» («House market») and etc.

The informativeness of an ergonym is perceived and evaluated differently by nominators and consumers. Many researchers agree that the nominators often exaggerate the importance of the advertising side of the ergonym, so they try to create bright and catchy names. From the point of view of the nominators, the most successful will be the names containing a lot of meanings. At the same time, it is the informativity of the ergonym that is much more important for the consumer. Therefore, as statistics show, there is currently a noticeable trend towards an increase in the number of informative ergonyms.

However, regardless of the type of ergonym, its main functions are informative and attractive, which are also in close interaction: thanks to the informativeness, ergonyms attract attention consumers. To implement these functions, the nominators use various means, including graphic design.

